

On the Cancer of Wild Animals

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Abstract

Cancer affects all animals containing eukaryotic cells. Less is known about the cancers that affect wild animals, since they move around and may not be easily observed for a long period of time. This review about cancers in wild animals may have useful data for the study of human cancers as well. Certain cancers in dinosaurs show that this metabolic disease is primitive and may have been around since the beginning of the multicellular organisms.

Keywords

Cancer, Wild Animals, Eukaryotic Cells, Multicellular Organisms

Introduction

Cancer

Cancer is a group of diseases that involve abnormal cell division and growth, with the potential to invade or spread to other parts of the body which is called metastasis. [28] Not all

tumors are cancerous. Benign tumors do not spread to other parts of the body. Possible symptoms include a lump, abnormal bleeding, prolonged cough, unexplained weight loss and a change in bowel movements. Although these symptoms may indicate cancer, they may have other causes. [30] Over 100 kinds of cancers affect humans and also mammalians. [29]

Tobacco use is the cause of around 22 percent of cancer deaths. Another 10 percent is due to obesity, poor diets, lack of physical activity and drinking alcohol. [31] Other factors include certain infections, exposure to ionizing radiation and environmental pollutants and also certain viruses and parasites. [32] In the developing world, nearly 20% of cancers are due to infections like hepatitis B, hepatitis C and human papillomavirus (HPV). These factors act by changing the genes of a cell. Typically many genetic changes are required before cancer develops. [33] Approximately 5 to 10 percent of cancers are because of inherited genetic defects from a person's parents. [34]

Materials and Methods

Cancer in Dinosaurs

Cancer is a disease that has been around for millions of years. In a 2003 study, researchers used fluoroscopy and computed tomography (CT) to screen over 10,000 dinosaur vertebrae specimens for tumors. They found tumors in approximately 3% of the Cretaceous hadrosaurs specimens, but did not find tumors in any other dinosaur species. The tumors included hemangiomas, desmoplastic fibroma, and osteoblastoma. [2]

In a research article conducted in 1999, metastatic cancer was found in only 1 out of 548 Edmontosaurus vertebrae sampled and was absent in all remaining samples. Hemangioma was present in 20 out of 669 Edmontosaurus vertebrae sampled and was absent in all 286 Corythosaurus vertebrae sampled as well as all 7,475 sauropods, ceratopsians, stegosaurs, theropoda, ornithomimids, and ankylosaurs vertebrae sampled. [3][4]

The statistically significant higher occurrence of hemangiomas found in hadrosaurs than in other dinosaur species suggests a genetic or environmental basis behind the pattern of tumor incidence. An example of an environmental factor could be the carcinogenic tannins, phenols, and resins found in the leaves consumed by these types of dinosaurs. [4]

Tasmanian devil Facial Tumor

Tasmanian Devils were driven to extinction on the Australian mainland thousands of years ago, after humans introduced dingoes to the continent. The remainder of the wild population has since inhabited the Australian island-state of Tasmania. In the mid 1990's the population reached an estimated 150,000 devils.[5] Nowadays, the animals are plagued by an infectious cancer known as Tasmanian devil facial tumor disease (DFTD). Since the emergence of the disease in 1996, the population has declined by more than 60 percent. [6]

This type of cancer is very unusual. The great majority of cancer cases in humans and animals arise from a series of mutations in a single precursor cell and its daughter cells. The process occurs over a period of years and does not involve contact with any other individuals. DFTD develops differently. It's transmitted from animal to animal and the cancer cells themselves are the infectious agent.

This phenomenon is called allograft transmission. An allograft is the term for the transfer of cells or tissue from one individual to another. An example in humans is organ

transplantation. The movement of cancer cells between animals has been confirmed by cellular and molecular studies. A normal devil cell contains 14 chromosomes.[7] DFTD tumor cells contain several very distinctive genetic changes and have only 13 chromosomes. Importantly, the tumors from every animal tested appear identical.[7] Researchers in Tasmania also found a devil with an unusual chromosomal abnormality in its non-tumorous tissue that did not appear in its tumor cells.[7] These findings strongly suggest that the cancer did not arise from the animals' own cells.[9][10]

A cancer similar to DFTD occurs in dogs, and is known as Canine Transmissible Venereal Tumor (CTVT). The immune system of dogs is capable of overcoming the disease, but devils do not seem to be able to do so. Low genetic diversity among Tasmanian devils results in close kinship and reduces their immune responses. In conclusion, transplanted cancer cells are more likely to survive, grow, and spread. [8][11]

Transmission can occur by biting, feeding on the same material, aggressive mating, and other social interactions. DFTD tumors mostly form on the face and/or in the oral cavity. The cancer can also metastasize to other areas of the body. Nearly 100% of infected devils die within 6 months of the onset of clinical signs.[8] Death results from an inability to feed, secondary infection, or symptoms associated with metastases.

Cancer in Sharks

George Washington University Medical Center researchers reported over thirty tumors found in elasmobranchs, a group of animals that includes sharks, rays, and skates. [13]

Cancer in Wild Fish

In August of 2012, an article was published that described the discovery of melanoma affecting a population of wild fish. *Plectropomus leopardus* which commonly called coral trout live along the Great Barrier reef. Because the reef is located directly under the largest known ozone hole, it is thought that the cancer is due to increased exposure of the fish to ultraviolet (UV) radiation. Ozone normally absorbs the damaging UV rays, but ozone depletion allows the rays to reach the surface of the earth and the fish. No other causes of the cancer were identified in this study. UV light is the single greatest risk factor for the development of melanoma in humans. [23]

Cancer in Naked Mole Rats

Naked mole rats live up to thirty years which is a long life in this species. [24] Although cancer incidence increases with age, this disease was not observed in this species. By studying naked mole rats, researchers hoped to discover the keys to cancer resistance.

Ironically, then, cases of cancer have been reported in naked mole rats. [25][26] These case reports indicate that naked mole rats are not resistant to cancer. One reason for this reported to be , hyaluronic acid, which was found to be much larger in naked mole rats than in other mammals. [27]

Conclusion

Almost all animals containing eukaryotic cells can get cancer. There has been some reports of cancer in Cretaceous hadrosaurs specimens, and this means cancer has been affecting dinosaurs as well. Tasmanian Devil Facial Tumor is an unusual cancer which is contagious

and it's transmitted from animal to animal, and the cancer cells themselves are the infectious agent. There have been some reports of cancer in sharks and wild fish which shows this disease can affect submarine animals too. The most eye catching cancer in wild animals is the type in naked mole rats which due to the high concentration of hyaluronic acid in their tissues and cell membranes, which can be of an important issue in human cancer treatment as well.

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